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Research Article

**IMPACT OF LABOR PAIN ON DEVELOPMENT OF
INTERACTION AMONG NEW BIRTHS & MOTHERS****Nizam Farid Chishti, Muhammad Sartaj Khan, Amen Liaqat**
UHS, Lahore.**Article Received:** February 2019**Accepted:** March 2019**Published:** April 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: This study aimed to assess that whether severity of the pain in labor has some impact of the growth of the interaction between neonates and mothers in females of our country.

Methodology: The research study conducted in the departments of obstetrics & gynecology in Mayo Hospital, Lahore from January to March 2019. In the duration of this study, interview of two hundred and twenty-five mothers having infants conducted. All these females were fulfilling the standard of inclusion in the case study.

Results: The mean scores of the interaction among mother and infant were significant statistically in accordance with the age of the mother, level of education and duration of the labor. There was no impact on the interaction because of type of labor. The disparity among the initial period of feeding through breasts and scores of interaction was much significant. The severity of the labor pain is not able to impact on the interaction of mother and her infant. But with the increase in the intensity of labor pain, the scores of interaction decrease.

Conclusion: The results showed that there should be the implementation of training programs for the interaction of mother and their infants especially who are with high age, low level of education & multigravida. There is also a suggestion to use the techniques which are painless during delivery.

Key Words: Methodology, interaction, implementation, obstetrics, gynecology, multigravida, breast, severity.

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INTRODUCTION:

The interaction among infant & mother is the best interpretation of the growth and wellbeing of the infant [1-3]. There is a determination that labor pain has an impact on the interaction of mother and infant [3], because childbirth accompanies with a severe amount of pain [4]. The studies of the past have displayed that traumatic labors like cesarean operations & utilizations of forceps and vacuum, delay in the creation on the bond among mother and infant just after the delivery. This is because of the long present excessive pain which intervenes the interest of mother in child & interferes the interaction [5, 6].

Different case works on the interaction of mother & infant have studied the long and short term impacts of the labor pain [4, 7]. The case works about this topic are very less in Pakistan. To understand whether there is any relationship among the intensity of pain & growth of the interaction among mother & her infant & to find out the other features that affect the interaction, may give valuable information. This study aimed to interrogate whether the intensity of the labor pain has an impact on the growth of interaction between infant and mother in Pakistani females.

METHODOLOGY:

This study conducted in Mayo hospital Lahore and the duration of this study was from January to March 2019. In this duration, two hundred and twenty five females with infants who were fulfilling the standard of the study were the part of this research. The average age of the mothers was 27.150 years. Majority of females (45.30%) were having the age from 16 to 25 years, (50.70%) females found with education of primary & 62.70% females were multigravida.

Inclusion standards for study:

1. No other complication in females after child birth.
2. Weight of infant as 2500 grams or over and birth after 38 to 42 weeks after pregnancy.

A special questionnaire was in use for the collection of the information. MIIAS, scale to determine the interaction among mothers and their infants was in use. The intensity of the labor pain was under evaluation by the VAS (visual analogue scale). The information of demography, number of deliveries, qualification, age & type of labor were available in the questionnaire. Stainton developed PIIAS (parent infant interaction assessment scale [8], Pek recently checked its reliability [9]. The interaction was under monitoring by these scales by our experts at regular intervals.

The grouping of the scale carried out into fifteen articles in the category of behavior with 0, 1 & 2 scores/ points. For the achievement of the precise point, the article providing the perfect description in the category of behavior during pain was under marking, by gathering the scores from every category, we obtained the total scores. We also obtained the scores to find out the requirement of the support of nurses in the interaction of mother and infant. 8-10 scores show that infant and mother are not in need of the support of nurse. 5 & 7 scores show that they were in need of support from nurses. 0 & 4 scores show that both of them are extremely in need of support from nurse. Cronbach's Alpha discovered 0.88 [9] in his research conducted by Pek [9], and 0.81 is in current work. The visual analogue scale is in widely use for the calculation of the perception of pain and intensity of the pain [10-12]. There are two anchors in this scale, zero for no pain and ten for extreme pain [13]. There was no intensity in pain with 0 centimeters, mild pain from 0.10 to 4.0 centimeters, medium/moderate from 4.10 to 7.0 centimeters and extreme/severe from 7.10 to 10 centimeters [12, 14].

Ethical committee of the hospital gave his approval to conduct this case work. All the participants gave their verbal consent to participate in case study. SPSS V.10 was in use for the analysis of the collected information. Averages & SD values were in use for the determination of quantitative information. The description of the categorical variables performed with the help of frequency. Student T test was in use for the comparison of the various averages. The significant P value was less than 0.050.

RESULTS:

The case work interrogated whether the intensity of labor pain & characteristics of mother like female age, level of qualification, duration of pain and type of labor have impacts on the growth of interaction among mothers and their infants. In this case work, when the age of mothers was younger (from 16 to 25 years) and their level of qualification increased, scores of interaction got increase, and there were less scores of interaction among mothers with multigravida. The mean scores of interaction among mother and her infant were significant statistically in accordance with the mother age, level of qualification & duration of labor. The type of labor is not able to impact on the interaction of mother an infant. The disparity between the starting duration of feeding through breasts & scores of interactions was important (Table-1).

Table-I: The average scores of interaction according to mothers' characteristics.

Characteristics		Mothers	Percentage	MBIES (average scores)	P-Value
Age (yrs)	16 to 25	102.0	45.30	8.040±2.400	
	26 to 35	99.0	44.00	7.880±2.020	
	36 and over	24.0	10.70	6.080±3.060	Sig*
Education level	illiterate	45.0	20.00	5.910±2.310	
	Literate and primary school	114.0	50.70	7.870±2.390	
	Secondary education	48.0	21.30	8.810±1.630	
	University	18.0	8.00	8.940±1.390	Sig*
Labor number	Primigravid	84.0	37.30	8.260±2.310	
	Multigravid	141.0	62.70	7.470±2.390	Sig*
Labor type	Vaginal	108.0	48.00	7.660±2.410	N-Sig**
	Caesarean	117.0	52.00	7.860±2.360	
Time to start breastfeeding	0 to 2 hours	115.0	51.10	7.480±2.870	
	3 to 4 hours	43.0	19.10	6.270±0.700	
	5 hours and above	67.0	29.80	9.200±1.020	Sig*
Total		225.0	100.00		

*Significant **Not significant

The intensity of the labor pain is not able to impact the interaction among mother and her infant (Table-2).

Table-II: The average pain scores of mothers according to VAS.

VAS	N	%	MBIES average scores	P
Slight pain	55.0	24.40	7.960±2.320	
Average pain	74.0	32.90	7.930±2.230	
Intense pain	96.0	42.70	7.530±2.530	N-Sig*
Total	225.0	100.00		

* Not significant

DISCUSSION:

The mothers with young age have more scores of interaction and the disparity among age of female and scores of interaction was significant statistically in current case study. Previous case studies showed the positive relation with pain and age of the mother [4]. This outcome may have association with the good health of the young females who have more mental as well as healthier resources to handle the pain of labor [4, 16, 17]. The results of this work are similar to the findings of previous studies. We concluded that when there is increase in the level of qualification of female, there is an increase in the scores of interaction and disparity among these two factors is significant.

Past case studies on the same literature have found that an important predictor of the sensitivity of mother is the qualification of mother [1, 18]. Our findings of the research were similar to those outcomes. The previous case studies displayed that with the increase in the duration of the labor, the tolerance to bear the pain decreases and it develops the negative behavior of mothers [15, 19-21]. We concluded that the type of labor have no impact on the interaction of mother and infant & the disparity among type of labor & interaction was not important statistically. This finding proved that type of labor was not an effectual factor on the relationship. This findings was also available in the previous case works. The disparity between the initiations of feeding through breasts & scores of interaction was not significant. Mothers providing 5 hours feeding through breast or more found with high scores of interaction. It is important to begin the feeding in 1 to 2 hours after birth [6]. The findings also showed that extreme labor pain have the ability to effect the interaction scores during the initial days of

complications and recovery [15]. The result of current work is consistent with this finding.

CONCLUSION:

The findings proved that young females with high level of qualification and feeding their babies through breasts within 5 hour after child birth have the high scores of interaction as compared to other females. There should be training programs during pregnancy about the interaction among females with high age, less qualification & multigravida. This case work proved that when the intensity of labor increases, it causes the decrease in scores of interaction but it is not much significant.

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